

IMPLEMENTATION OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN TEACHING TOURISM ENGLISH IN PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *The following research work aims to investigate on the use of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in teaching tourism for the students of vocational colleges. The knowledge about English Language Teaching (ELT) methods/approaches will guide the action of teachers of English in classroom. The reasons in choosing the best ELT method/approach will be depended on various factors. However, the ELT method/approach is supposed to facilitate the students to be competence in English. Using the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is aimed to carter the students' need in communicative competence. Curriculum, students' needs and facilities are extents to call CLT in ELT at of English Department concentration in tourism and hospitality industry. In the paper the author focuses on the communicative language teaching as one of the trend approach, specific features of tourism English, some examples for CLT, and designed lesson plan.*

Keywords: *Tourism, teaching, methodologists, key, researches, language.*

Some decades ago, there was very different view on teaching English in Uzbekistan. It was believed that grammatical structure and rules are much more important in language learning process than the acquisition of new lexical items. Regardless the fact that teaching vocabulary can seem a very daunting process especially when talking about a foreign language, many linguists and methodologists have made affords to give emphasis on how it should be taught and learned. As a teacher, we play key role in increasing students' motivation in language learning by the way we present new words.

According to the view of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoev, we should create the necessary conditions for the youth to acquire deep knowledge and modern professions and train a highly qualified workforce, young specialists capable of taking on responsibility for the future and further development of the country. In addition, our President

states that in the system of education we attach a great importance to teaching students not merely liberal arts and vocational skills, but also required learning of foreign languages. Taking into consideration the above-mentioned the main goal of teaching learners has become to encourage children to use the target language in their life.

According to advocates of the CLT approach, grammar is not sufficient for proper communication. What Chomsky called linguistic competence is no longer seen as the basic principle and goal for learning a language. Instead, communicative competence becomes, in 1972, the goal of EFL learning. Dell Hymes, one of the revolutionary linguistic thinkers of the decade, argued that in order to be fluent and accurate in a certain language, students should master communicative and language functions. What we teach should reflect-real life language situations. Therefore, the memorization and drilling that were the focus of the old traditional methods are no longer the focus of the language teacher.

Evidently, these days in Uzbekistan the real concern has to do more with the function of English and its practical and everyday use for communication.

So, benefits and drawbacks of using CLT, as well as exploring the effective ways of implementation in teaching tourism English is considered as an **actuality of the theme of the graduation project work**.

The aim of the work is to familiarize the teachers of the republic with some features of CLT in teaching tourism English, and the work carries out the following **tasks**:

- to introduce with some CLT activities and to implement them in the classroom;
- to investigate on creating communicative atmosphere;
- to highlight the benefits of communicative approach in improving students' language skills and raising communicative competence

Theoretical and practical value of the work

Chapter 1 deals with general notions and concepts of CLT and teaching tourism English, therefore the work could serve as an informative source for those who do researches concerning teaching tourism English by using communicative approach.

The **practical** part might be a useful manual for teachers while teaching vocabulary and speaking skills.

This work can serve as theoretical and practical source for the bachelors and post-graduates who are going to make research work on this topic.

The structure of the research

The work consists of Introduction, 2 chapters, Conclusion and the list of used literature. **Introduction** has information about general view of the theme, reveals the aim, duties, methods, theoretical and practical value of the work. Each chapter consists of two paragraphs. **Chapter I** is dedicated to the theoretical explanation of CLT. **Chapter II** has demonstrated practical ways of using various communicative activities in teaching tourism english in vocatioanl colleges.

Conclusion combines the main and significant results of our investigation.

The list of used literature shows the scientific works, articles and thesis used for the work.

CHAPTER 1. Communicative Language Teaching in Teaching Tourism English

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) has enormous intuitive appeal. Despite this, I have come to believe that at the heart of CLT - especially in fundamentalist versions of it - we find a naive, even impoverished view of language. To demonstrate what I mean, let me examine six propositions upon which I think CLT is based. I am going to argue that if these propositions are true at all, they are only superficially and trivially true - and true only in essentially uninteresting ways. In other words, they are just as true as statements like "When people speak, they use words". Such a statement tells us nothing about what kinds of relationships there may be between words, how people learn to assemble them into larger units, or what else they do to construct or interpret meaning. I will try to show this through six counter-propositions. Then - finally -I will briefly suggest an alternative - and also suggest reasons why pluralist methodologies are more likely to be successful than any single orthodoxy.

Before the 1970's in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, teachers focused on grammar and translation. The principles of this approach reflected the needs of society, because at that time people learned languages generally for translation rather than for communication. Thus, when people started to value communication, the Communicative Language Teaching approach was created. In this new era of technological development, schools have had to adapt themselves to the needs of our new technology-based society. Therefore, EFL classes have been trying to simulate the real world, and have started incorporating technology-based instruction in their curricula.

There are some of the historical realities that precipitated these pedagogic changes: during the seventies, the European common market needed more workers who could communicate effectively using other languages; therefore, language schools began to respond to these economic imperatives. Some linguists started rethinking the methods that were used in language pedagogy, and tried to find alternative approaches to the teaching of foreign languages. As a result of this re-evaluation, linguists established the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Approach as an alternative method, in which person-to-person communication is both a principle and a goal.

1.1. General characteristics and principles of Communicative Language Teaching Approach

Good teaching is regarded as correct use of the method and its prescribed principles and techniques. Roles of teachers and learners, as well as the type of activities and teaching techniques to be used in the classroom are generally prescribed. Richards & Rodgers (2001:244) stated that:

“From the survey of approaches and methods, we have seen that the history of language teaching in the last one hundred years has been characterized by a search for more effective ways of teaching second or foreign language. The commonest solution to the “language teaching problem” was seen to lie in the adoption of a new teaching approach or methods. One result of this trend was the era of so called designer or brand-name methods, that is, packaged solutions that can be described and marketed for use anywhere in the world. Thus, the Direct Methods was enthusiastically embraced in the early part of the twentieth century as an improvement over Grammar Translation. In the 1950s the Audiolingual Methods began to fade in the 1970s, particularly in the United States, a variety of guru-led methods emerged to fill the vacuum created by the discrediting of Audiolingualism, such as the Silent Way, Total Physical Response, and Suggestopedia. While these had declined substantially by the 1990s, new “breakthrough” continue to be announced from time to time, such as Task-Based Instruction, Neurolinguistic Programming, and Multiple Intelligences, and these attract varying level of support. Mainstream language teaching on both sides of the Atlantic, however, opted, for Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) as the recommended basis for language teaching methodology in the 1980s and it continues to be considered the most plausible basis for language teaching today,

although CLT is today understood to mean little more than a set of vary general principles that can be applied and interpreted in a variety of ways”.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. T. “O'zbekiston” 2016.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining “Ta'lim to'g'risida” qonuni. T – 2020
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 25 yanvardagi «Umumiy o'rta, o'rta maxsus va professional ta'limi tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida»gi PF-5313-sonli Farmoni.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 6 sentyabrdagi “Professional ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirishga doir qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida”gi PF-5812-son Farmoni
5. Jalolov, J., Makhkamova, G., Ashurov, Sh. English Language Teaching Methodology, Tashkent-2015 Azar B. Sh. Fun with grammar. New York. 2000
6. Avedon, M.E., & Brian, B. S.(1971). Learning Through Games. The Study of Games. John Wiley & Sons